

IMPLEMENTATION OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY OPPORTUNITIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation. The article is about the relevance of the usage of information and communication technologies that makes it possible to solve the main contradiction of the modern education system - the contradiction between the rapid rate of increase in knowledge in the modern world and the limited possibilities of their assimilation by the individual. Now everyone understands that the Internet has colossal information capabilities and no less impressive services. But we must not forget that, no matter what properties this or that means of education, the information-subject environment possesses, didactic tasks, and the features of the cognitive activity of students, due to certain goals of education, are primary. The Internet, with all its capabilities and resources, is one of the means of realizing these goals and objectives.

Keywords: *information, communication technologies, educational process.*

Аннотация. В статье говорится об актуальности использования информационно-коммуникационных технологий, позволяющих решить главное противоречие современной системы образования - противоречие между быстрыми темпами роста знаний в современном мире и ограниченными возможностями их усвоения индивидуумом. Сейчас все понимают, что Интернет обладает колоссальными информационными возможностями и не менее впечатляющими услугами, но нельзя забывать, что какими бы свойствами ни обладало то или иное средство обучения, информационно-предметная среда, дидактические задачи, особенности познавательной деятельности учащихся в силу определенных целей обучения являются первичными. Интернет со всеми его возможностями и ресурсами является одним из средств реализации этих целей и задач.

Ключевые слова: *информация, коммуникационные технологии, образовательный процесс.*

Annotatsiya. Maqolada zamonaviy ta'lim tizimining asosiy qarama-qarshiligini - zamonaviy dunyoda bilimlarning tez o'sish sur'ati va ularni o'zlashtirishning cheklangan imkoniyatlari o'rtasidagi ziddiyatni hal qilishga imkon beradigan axborot-kommunikatsiya texnologiyalaridan foydalanishning dolzarbligi haqida. shaxs tomonidan. Endi hamma Internet ulkan axborot imkoniyatlariga va undan kam bo'lgan ta'sirchan xizmatlarga ega ekanligini tushunadi. Lekin shuni unutmasligimiz kerakki, u yoki bu ta'lim vositalari, axborot-sub'ekt muhiti qanday xususiyatlarga ega bo'lishidan qat'i nazar, didaktik vazifalar, ta'limning ma'lum maqsadlaridan kelib chiqqan holda o'quvchilarning bilish faoliyatining xususiyatlari birlamchi hisoblanadi. Internet o'zining barcha imkoniyatlari va resurslari bilan ana shu maqsad va vazifalarni amalga oshirish vositalaridan biridir.

Kalit so'zlar: *axborot, kommunikatsiya texnologiyalari, o'quv jarayoni.*

At the present stage of higher education reforms, serious changes are associated with the introduction of information and communication technologies in the educational process. The implementation of the reform is carried out by higher education through the solution of methodological and organizational tasks. It is the use of information and communication technologies that makes it possible to solve the main contradiction of the modern education system - the contradiction between the rapid rate of increase in knowledge in the modern world and the limited possibilities of their assimilation by the individual. Many students prefer to use a computer in the process of performing "great" tasks (writing an essay, term paper, abstract) associated with writing large texts. In this situation, the computer is used as an activity partner and at the same time an information as well as technical support tool. Using computer tools, students:

- 1) enter new textual information;
- 2) get access to extensive information in their native and foreign languages, due to reference and networks, using, if necessary, machine translation systems;
- 3) edit and improve written works with the help of programs such as "text editor", spellers and document templates;
- 4) work with interactive text generation programs and automatic text processing systems (abstract summarizing, etc.);
- 5) systematize and supplement textual information with tables, graphs, diagrams and drawings.

The main purpose of the computer as a tool for educational and cognitive activity is to provide maximum support in mastering the language, which allows the student to move on to more rational forms of learning that bridge the gap between acquiring knowledge and their actual assimilation. Students use a PC as an activity tool not only to receive information and technical support, but also to organize distance learning communication using computer telecommunication networks. The computer makes it possible to implement various forms of interpersonal mediated communication; verbal contact communication (net-conferences) and written distant communication (e-mail); individual communication (personal correspondence) and group communication (zoom). Only modern computer technologies make it possible to implement part-time language teaching in the form of distance learning (learning at a distance), which is successfully carried out both within the framework of individual inter-university programs and on the scale of entire educational institutions (for example, the Open University of London in the UK, the National Technological University of London Colorado in the USA). The form of distance learning is also interesting in that it allows you to make the process of language acquisition more natural in terms of the conditions for its course, since the language is not studied in the classroom at the same time by a large number of students within the time allotted for the lesson, but individually, moreover, using various organizational forms of work. . Students acquire some autonomy, not only physical, but also social and psychological, choosing the most comfortable and natural conditions for learning. It can

be concluded that the use of a computer in the process of mastering a language creates conditions for foreign language communication, provides wide access to information and helps in independent learning of a foreign language. Today's software corporations understand that the demand for training software is growing exponentially.

Our task is for the convenience of using this material by students and teachers, to combine all this as much as possible within the framework of one program. If these are large multimedia programs, then describe by topic what grammatical, lexical or phonetic material can be found in this program, what exercises this product provides. Now everyone understands that the Internet has colossal information capabilities and no less impressive services. But we must not forget that, no matter what properties this or that means of education, the information-subject environment possesses, didactic tasks, the features of the cognitive activity of students, due to certain goals of education, are primary. The Internet, with all its capabilities and resources, is one of the means of realizing these goals and objectives. At the moment, there are a large number of sites dedicated to the teacher of foreign languages. On such sites you can find: ready-made lessons, newspaper articles, various thematic texts, exercises, grammar explanations, audio books. However, interactive educational computer-mediated communication of a teacher and a student, when the acquired knowledge becomes the most active, is often opposed to passive acquisition of knowledge. Mediated communication changes not only the structure, but also the nature of traditional communication. It should be noted that real ways to solve problems associated with a huge amount of educational material to be mastered and controlled, as well as with differential learning is the intensification and individualization of learning, carried out in three directions:

- development of new teaching methods and techniques;
- introduction of new forms of organization of the educational process (taking into account the requirement to increase the proportion of students' independent work);
- more intensive use of LLP in the practice of teaching, including computer.

Recently, scientific research and publications that examine the experience of teachers and methodologists indicate that the effectiveness of teaching foreign languages can be significantly improved through the introduction of new pedagogical technologies, in particular, information and communication technologies. Thus, almost every discipline should use computer technology to increase the level of student knowledge, speed up and improve the presentation of material, and enhance learning. This will increase the efficiency of both full-time and, in particular, part-time education, where a large amount of material is required to be submitted in the shortest possible time.

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